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MODERN TRENDS IN THE TRANSPORT SYSTEM OF URGENCH CITY INFRASTRUCTURE

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Abstract: This article addresses the growing relevance of traffic flow issues, including the traffic congestion problems faced in various regions and cities of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Examining all transport-related issues occurring in our country reveals a variety of underlying causes. For example, work is being carried out in Khorezm region based on a program for studying traffic flow.

In studying traffic flow, the movement patterns of vehicles are primarily analyzed; alongside the study of traffic flow in Urgench city, this process is also contributing to urban environmental pollution. The busiest intersections in Urgench city were identified, traffic intensity was measured during peak hours of the day, the results were analyzed, and relevant proposals and recommendations were developed.

Keywords: flow, intensity, intersection, junction, public transport, transport infrastructure, bus.

INTRODUCTION. The streets selected as the research area — Pahlavon Mahmud Street and Baynalminalchi Street — reflect the historical and socio-cultural layers of Urgench city. Pahlavon Mahmud Street is named after the famous historical figure of Khorezm, the poet, philosopher and wrestler Pahlavon Mahmud, while Baynalminalchi Street belongs to a toponymic layer representing the internationalist ideas and multi-ethnic social environment of the former era. In this regard, these streets are significant not only from the perspective of traffic movement, but also in terms of urban historical memory and naming traditions. The high social and economic importance of the urban transport sector is one of its most essential characteristics. The overall development of the

economy and the quality of life of all segments of the population depend on the effective functioning of this system. At the same time, the rapid increase in traffic volume on urban road networks leads to a reduction in street throughput capacity, a decrease in vehicle speeds, and the emergence of traffic congestion at most at-grade intersections. Such conditions result in increased fuel consumption, loss of time for passengers, and the deterioration of economic, social, environmental, and sanitary-hygienic conditions. Introducing advanced methods of traffic flow management makes it possible to achieve the greatest effect in the shortest time and to make maximum use of the capacity of the urban road network.

1.1-rasm. Intersection of "Pahlavon Mahmud" and "Baynalminal" streets in Urgench city

In this regard, the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026, approved by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, sets forth the following objectives: “to reduce road accidents and fatalities through the improvement of road infrastructure and the creation of safe movement conditions, including the full digitalization of the traffic management system and ensuring broad public participation in activities in this field” [1].

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY. A number of CIS and foreign scholars have presented extensive data and formed important scientific-practical conclusions in their research on the topic of this study. Among domestic scholars, V.V. Silyanov, V.F. Babkov, O.V. Andreyev, V.A. Cherepanov, R.V. Gorbanev, and I.S. Baydjanov have conducted research on vehicular traffic intensity and road throughput capacity.

On the topics of road safety, urban transport planning, and measures to ensure safe movement at transport nodes, a number of foreign and domestic scholars have conducted

research, including: D.N. Ilasov, A.V. Kossov, I.A. Bakhirov, Ye.N. Borovik, D.S. Martyakhin, A. Eshonqulov, I.S. Sodiqov, A. Sattorov, S.A. Nishonov, M.O. Qodirkhonov, Sh.A. Mirkhojaye, and A.R. Qodirova.

The following methods are envisaged for use in the research:

Observation — applicable to studying and analyzing traffic congestion on urban road networks.

Comparative analysis — involves determining the optimal solution among proposals made and projects implemented to date by comparing multiple scientific data sources.

RESULTS. The following method is used to study and analyze traffic flow: Type 1 is a single road (forward and reverse direction, Figure 1); Type 2 is a T-junction or three-way road (entry and exit at the junction, Figure 2); Type 3 is a crossroads or four-way junction (turning at the junction, going straight, turning left, right, and making U-turns, Figure 3) [4].

A university working group was established for the purpose of creating a convenient transport system in Urgench city. Traffic intensity measurement work via observation was planned at the intersection of “Baynalminal” Street and “Pahlavon Mahmud” Street, one of the busiest intersections in the city. Measurements were carried out on working days during peak hours: from 8:30 to 9:30, from 12:30 to 13:30, and from 17:30 to 18:30, to determine the throughput capacity of the intersection. Type 3 was used — covering vehicles turning at the intersection, going straight, and turning left, right, and making

U-turns. Vehicles were categorized into groups by make.

DISCUSSION. During the study of traffic flow, vehicles were counted separately by hour, and the counted numbers were recorded in tabular form (Table 1). The intersection or single road was numbered to avoid confusion. For a Type 3 intersection, there are 16 directions (1, 2, ... 16); vehicles of each make passing through each numbered direction were added to that number’s count. Each hour was counted separately and a total was calculated.

Hourly traffic intensity of vehicles at the “Pahlavon Mahmud”–“Baynalminal” intersection.

Table 1

Yo’nalish	N_{yena} veh/hr	N_{yuka} veh/hr	N_{avtb} veh/hr	N_{tv} veh/hr	N_{mot} units/hr
1	85	2	-	-	-
2	658	9	-	-	5
3	148	2	-	-	-
4	190	1	14	-	1
5	581	5	26	4	1
6	177	1	-	-	2
7	180	2	-	-	2
8	719	7	15	-	5
9	215	2	22	-	1
10	645	36	40	-	2
11	745	13	39	3	1
12	145	1	3	-	-
Total	4488	81	159	7	20

Figure 1.2. Conditional cartogram of traffic intensity at the intersection. “Pahlavon Mahmud”–“Baynalminal” streets intersection.

Figure 1.3. 1-hour traffic flow at the “Pahlavon Mahmud”–“Baynalminal” streets intersection from 8:30 to 9:30.

Based on the test results, we found that traffic flow varies depending on the time of day. For example, we observed that traffic flow increases significantly during peak hours.

CONCLUSION. The research results showed that the increase in traffic flow in Urgench city has

led to intensifying congestion during peak hours of the day. The main causes identified include the narrowness of streets and roads, insufficient numbers of bridges and underpasses, and the mixing of public transport, taxis, and passenger vehicles in a single traffic stream. For this reason, it is necessary to improve the public transport system, establish dedicated bus lanes, and develop a separate system to regulate the movement of taxis and unscheduled passenger vehicles. Furthermore, for the purpose of improving traffic flow, the construction of additional bridges, underpasses, and dedicated traffic lanes is of great importance. These measures will serve to improve the efficiency of the city's transport infrastructure and ensure road safety.

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